

TRAINING FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS BASED ON
INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

Esemuratov Azizbek Abdimurat uli

Independent researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13729343>

ABSTRACT: This article examines the issues of training future English language teachers. The importance of pedagogical innovations and the effective results of their use were discussed.

Keywords: computer technologies, pedagogical innovation, information technologies, innovative environment, project methodology.

Today, the modernization of educational content in our country is connected with innovative processes in the organization of teaching foreign languages, as well as English. Pedagogical innovations are also used in the training of future English language teachers. Pedagogical innovation has its own specific description. The dimensions of pedagogical innovations that serve to prepare future English language teachers and shape their creative activities include: novelty, optimality of innovative methods, the ability to give high results, and the ability to creatively apply them in public experience.

The priority direction of modern educational development is the humanistic direction of education, in which personal potential (principle) takes the leading place. Taking into account the needs and interests of the student includes the implementation of a differentiated approach to learning. Attention is also paid to the student, his personality and his unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose the methods and forms of organizing the educational activities of students in a way that optimally matches the goal of personal development.

One of the technologies that provides person-oriented education is the project method as a method of developing creativity, cognitive activity and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. According to M.E. Breygina, projects can be divided into collective, oral, individual, written and Internet projects. In real practice, it is often necessary to deal with a variety of projects that are creative, practiceoriented, and informative. Project work is a multi-level approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method helps to develop active independent thinking of future English language teachers and directs them to joint scientific and research work. Also, project-based teaching is relevant because it teaches students to cooperate, develops creative skills and activates students. In general,

the continuity of teaching and learning is observed in the project-based learning process.

The method of the project is to develop the communication skills of future English language teachers, communication culture, to form thoughts briefly and easily, to tolerate the opinions of communication partners, to develop the ability to receive information from various sources, to process it using modern computer technologies, and to create a language environment that provides a natural need to communicate in English. The project form of the lesson is one of the modern technologies that allow future English teachers to apply their accumulated knowledge on the subject. Future English teachers expand the boundaries of language knowledge, gain experience in its practical use, learn to listen and hear English speech, and learn to understand each other while defending projects. Future English teachers work with literature, dictionaries and computers, thus creating the possibility of direct contact only with the English language [1].

Working on a project is a creative process. Future English language teachers are engaged in the search for a solution to a problem independently or under the guidance of a teacher, which requires not only knowledge of the language, but also acquisition of language knowledge, acquisition of creative, communicative and intellectual skills.

In English classes, the project method can be used as part of the program material for almost any subject. Working on projects develops imagination, creative thinking, independence and other personal qualities. Modern technology also includes collaborative technology. The main idea is to create conditions for active joint activities of future English language teachers in various educational situations. Students are grouped into groups of 3-4 people, they are given one task and each of them is assigned a role. Each student is responsible not only for the result of his work, but also for the result of the whole group. Therefore, weak students try to find what they do not understand from strong ones, and strong students try to make the weak ones understand the task thoroughly. And the whole group will benefit because the gaps will be eliminated together [2].

Failure to create an innovative environment in a higher education institution also has a drastic impact on the quality of training future English language teachers. This, in turn, causes their creativity to fail to develop and fade away during their training. Due to the consistent adoption of innovations by future English language teachers, the level of contradictions between teachers

working in a friendly environment in the pedagogical team will decrease, and old patterns in professional activity will be eliminated. In the innovative environment of the educational institution, the attitude of the teacher to innovation is clearly manifested. Also, the introduction of information technologies in English language classes significantly improves the process of information perception and processing. Thanks to the computer, Internet and multimedia tools, students are given the opportunity to master a large amount of information with subsequent analysis and sorting. The motivational basis of educational activity has also been significantly expanded. In the conditions of using multimedia, students get information from newspapers and television, conduct interviews and hold teleconferences.

Pedagogical innovation - making changes in the process of human education. They are aimed at improving and developing the entire education and training system. The main components of the innovative approach to education from the point of view of pedagogy are the activity approach. This approach is based on the idea that the functioning and development of the individual, as well as the interpersonal relations of students, are mediated by the goals, content and tasks of socially significant activities.

Active learning. It is based on the fact that the student is increasingly faced with the need to solve problem situations in real life. This method is aimed at personal development, self-organization, self-development. The basic principle is that the learner is the creator of his own knowledge. Active learning is definitely a priority in the current phase of English language teaching. After all, effective management of educational activities is possible only based on the active mental activity of students [3].

Teaching future English language teachers with the help of innovative technologies involves the introduction of a number of psychological approaches: cognitive, positive, emotional, motivational, optimistic, technological. All these approaches are aimed at future English teachers. Teaching English using the Internet. Information and communication technologies have begun to be introduced into the educational process, and the use of information technologies in English language classes is an effective factor in the development of student motivation [4].

• Today, the prospects for using Internet technologies are very wide. They are as follows:

- Correspondence with residents of English-speaking countries by e-mail;

- Participation in such international conferences, seminars and other network projects;

- Creation and posting of web sites and presentations on the network - these can be created jointly by the teacher and the student. In addition, it is possible to exchange presentations between teachers from different countries.

The creation of Internet resources is of interest to future English language teachers because of its novelty, relevance and creativity. Organization of cognitive activities of students in small groups gives each student the opportunity to show his activity. In order to achieve maximum effectiveness, it is necessary to use innovative, including, of course, various media-educational technologies in the educational process, thereby increasing the motivation and independence of future English language teachers [5].

Also, project methodology plays an important role in the educational process. Issues of integration of educational subjects are developed and communication with studied topics is provided. In the process of project work, a systematic approach to teaching is implemented more fully, educational tasks are coordinated, theory and practice are combined. Learning projects are more common in foreign language classes. These projects are designed for use in a specific lesson and have specific objectives. The task of the teacher: to correctly formulate the topics of the projects, to determine the scope of the necessary questions aimed at the implementation of the goals and tasks of a particular lesson. "My favorite book", "Favorite movie", "My vacation", "My friend", "Holidays", "Going to an exhibition", "Travel", "TV", "Movie", "Pets", "New Year", "My favorite season" and other educational project topics can be used as an example [6].

In conclusion, the effectiveness of using pedagogical innovations in the training of future English language teachers, the introduction of information technologies in English language classes, and the use of project methodology in the formation and improvement of the basic skills of speech activity of future English language teachers can be emphasized once again.

References:

1. Dusheina T.V. "Project methodology in foreign language lessons". IYASH, 2013, No. 5.
2. V.B. Popov "Internet technologies and development of education" Voronezh, VSPU, 2011.
3. Kiryagina, M. E. (2012). Pedagogical innovations in education. Bulletin of the Kazan Technological University, 15(18).

4. Nishonaliev U. Innovative pedagogical technologies of education and development. / Sat. materials of the scientific-practical conference "Actual issues of professional education of youth". - Alma-Ata: Rep. publisher cab. Kazakh acad. education to them. I.Altynsarina, 2010. -S. 235-240.
5. Potapova R.K. New information technologies and philology. SPB., 2014.
6. Ibragimova, G. N. (2015). Formation of creative abilities of students with the help of pedagogical innovations. 7. www.ziyonet.uz

